

Reactivities of some aromatic aldehydes towards multitude of inorganic oxidants containing elements belonging to different parts of periodic classification in highly acidic, acidic buffer and alkaline media

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Manuscript received 08 November 2013, accepted 07 January 2014

Abstract : This communication narrates the reactivities of different aromatic aldehydes ($\text{XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CHO}$, where X = -H, -NO₂, -Cl and -OMe) towards inorganic oxidants containing elements belonging to different parts of periodic classification in highly acidic, acidic buffer and alkaline media. The electron transfer reactions involving the substrates and oxidants focus on the studies during the period 1982-2012. The reactions have been investigated over wide range of experimental conditions. Oxidation of aromatic aldehydes by vanadium(V), chromium(VI), manganese(VII), bromate and iridium(IV) have been carried out in acidic medium whereas those by dihydrogentelluratometallate(III) ($[\text{M}^{\text{III}}(\text{H}_2\text{TeO}_6)_2]^{5-}$, where $\text{M}^{\text{III}} = \text{Cu}^{\text{III}}$ and Ag^{III}) and hexacyanoferrate(III) have been studied in alkaline medium. Kinetics and mechanistic features associated with electron transfer behaviors have been included and duly analyzed.

Keywords : Reactivity, aromatic aldehydes, inorganic oxidants, electron transfer reactions, kinetics and mechanism.

Introduction

The chemical literature on oxidation of organic compounds by transition metal ions is very extensive. Useful information about the mechanism of oxidation-reduction reactions is available in some earlier reviews¹⁻⁷. A number of studies on oxidation of aromatic aldehydes by different transition metal ion oxidants are reported over a span of time period starting from 1982. However, no attempt has been made to correlate all the results in a single review article. Hence this review article aims at documenting the progress in the field of oxidation of aromatic aldehydes mainly by different transition metal ion oxidants under different experimental conditions from 1982 to till date. The kinetics of the oxidation of aromatic aldehydes by several oxidants other than non-transition metal ions like permonosulphate⁸, *N*-chlorosuccinimide⁹, butyl triphenyl phosphonium dichromate¹⁰, *N*-bromonicotinamide¹¹, perborate¹², permonophosphoric acid¹³, *N*-bromobenzamide¹⁴ and pyridinium fluorochromate^{15a} have been reported. A convenient and efficient application of

H₂O₂ in ionic liquids for the oxidation of hydroxylated and methoxylated benzaldehydes to the corresponding phenols where good yield of products are obtained is also described^{15b}. The present review also deals with the reactivity of some aromatic aldehydes towards a few transition metal ion oxidants such as vanadium(V), chromium(VI), manganese(VII), iridium(IV), copper(III), silver(III) and iron(III) in highly acidic, acidic buffer and alkaline media. Salient features of the oxidation of the substrates by different oxidants have been described and analyzed. Finally, an attempt has been made to correlate the oxidation processes.

Experimental

Kinetics of the oxidation of aromatic aldehydes by vanadium(V)¹⁶, permanganate¹⁷ and bromate¹⁸ were followed titrimetrically whereas by chromium(VI)¹⁹ and iridium(IV)²⁰ spectrophotometrically at 380 nm and 488 nm respectively using a cell of path length 1 cm in a Perkin-Elmer digital spectrophotometer in acid medium. On the other hand oxidations by $[\text{M}^{\text{III}}(\text{H}_2\text{TeO}_6)_2]^{5-}$ were

investigated²¹ titrimetrically in alkaline medium. Outer-sphere reduction of hexacyanoferrate(III) by aromatic aldehydes were also studied²² in alkaline medium and the rates of disappearance of hexacyanoferrate(III) were followed at 420 nm.

Benzaldehyde-*d*₁ was prepared²⁰ by the reaction between benzil and lithium aluminium deuteride at 293 K followed by the reaction with Rochelle salt solution to give dihydrobenzoin-*d*₂ : m.p. 118–120 °C; ¹H NMR (60 MHz) δ CDCl₃ : 2.2 (1H, broad, OH) and 7.2–8.0 (5H, complex multiplet, aromatic H). Lead tetraacetate was then added to a solution of dihydrobenzoin-*d*₂ at 293 K. The reaction mixture was treated with water and then distilled to obtain colorless oil, IR ν_{max} (film) : 2100 and 2050 cm⁻¹ reported 4.76 and 4.83 μm; ¹H NMR δ (CCl₄) : 7.2–7.9 (m, aromatic H), no signal for aldehyde H.

Cyclic voltammetric experiments were performed by a Bio Analytical System (BAS) CV 27 instrument in a dry argon atmosphere using three electrode configuration. A cyclic voltammogram of bis(dihydrogentellurato)copper(III) solution in alkaline medium containing lithium perchlorate showed²¹ an irreversible reduction at -0.506 V at 298 K, however, bis(dihydrogentellurato)silver(III) shows the same at -0.571 V under similar experimental conditions. In the electrochemical processes the results were cited with reference to the standard one-electron redox system of ferrocene-ferrocenium under comparable conditions. The current height of the voltammogram indicated that the reduction of copper(III) had taken place through a one-electron transfer process whereas under the same experimental conditions silver(III) species undergoes a one-step two electron reduction process²¹.

EPR spectra were recorded with a Varian (model E112) spectrometer. The spectra of the reaction mixture at 298

K involving dihydrogentelluratocuprate(III) and benzaldehyde were recorded²¹ at 9.45 GHz.

Results

Oxidation by vanadium(V) :

The mechanism of the oxidation of benzaldehyde and its substituted derivatives by vanadium(V) was studied in perchloric acid medium¹⁶. The progress of the reaction was monitored by measuring the absorbance of the reaction mixture near the absorption maximum of vanadium(V) at 340 nm. The increase in absorbance with increase in substrate concentrations as well as the non-linear behavior of pseudo-first order rate constant as a function of changing initial [substrate] indicated the formation of an intermediate vanadium(V)-substrate complex. The pseudo-first order rate constant is independent of the initial vanadium(V) concentration in each case. The rate of the reaction is found to be proportional to the first power of oxidant and hydrogen ion concentrations. The effect of substituents on the reaction rate was studied using benzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehyde in 15% (v/v) acetic acid medium. The kinetic results for the oxidation of benzaldehyde at 303 K are mentioned in Table 1. Among the different substituted benzaldehydes, CH₃O- compound reacts at faster rate than the corresponding NO₂- and Cl-substituted derivatives¹⁶. The pseudo-first order rate constants follow the order : -OCH₃ > -H > -NO₂ > -Cl (Table 2).

Vanadium(V) exists as the cationic form in acid medium. In the low acidity region [H⁺] ≤ 0.1 M, vanadium(V) remains as the hydrated form, V(OH)₄⁺. However, at much higher acidity [H⁺] ≥ 2.1 M, it exists as the protonated forms V(OH)₃²⁺ and V(OH)₂³⁺. The protonated forms are assumed to be effective oxidant species^{23,24}.

Table 1. The values of second order-rate constants ($k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{S}]$), disproportionation constants (k) for the slow step and equilibrium constant (K) for the fast step for the oxidation of benzaldehyde by different oxidant in acid medium at 313 K

Oxidant	[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ² k_2 (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	10 ⁴ k (s ⁻¹)	K	Ref.
Vanadium(V)	2.1	–	0.606 ± 0.017	27.5 ± 0.74	16
Chromium(VI)	1.0	–	2.80 ± 0.08	14.0 ± 0.42	19
Permanganate	0.1	–	7.93 ± 0.27	0.11 ± 0.004	17
Bromate ^a	–	–	4.55 ± 0.17	10.7 ± 0.38	18
Hexachloroiridate(IV)	5.37 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.87 ± 0.06	–	–	20

The errors correspond to two least-squares standard deviations (±2σ). ^aThe reactions were performed in 70% (v/v) AcOH medium.

Table 2. Effect of substituents on the oxidation of benzaldehyde by V^V, Cr^{VI}, MnO₄⁻ and BrO₃⁻ in acid medium

Substrate	10 ⁴ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)			
	^b V ^V (Ref. 16)	^c Cr ^{VI} (Ref. 19)	^d MnO ₄ ⁻ (Ref. 17)	^e BrO ₃ ⁻ (Ref. 18)
Benzaldehyde	0.450 ± 0.013	1.830 ± 0.005	16.95 ± 0.512	2.330 ± 0.097
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	-	-	-	3.14 ± 0.147
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	-	8.52 ± 0.232	11.30 ± 0.341	4.223 ± 0.160
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	0.295 ± 0.008	13.86 ± 0.360	9.432 ± 0.414	6.900 ± 0.241
<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	-	-	-	1.570 ± 0.055
<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	-	3.480 ± 0.083	14.75 ± 0.565	2.180 ± 0.092
<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	0.126 ± 0.003	2.526 ± 0.068	15.30 ± 0.682	1.150 ± 0.041
<i>o</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde	-	-	-	-
<i>m</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde	-	3.150 ± 0.072	19.76 ± 0.823	-
<i>p</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde	1.920 ± 0.046	0.516 ± 0.012	27.72 ± 1.325	0.333 ± 0.009

The errors correspond to two least-squares standard deviations ($\pm 2\sigma$).

^b[V^V] = 1.0 × 10⁻², [PhCHO] = 6.0 × 10⁻² and [HClO₄] = 2.1 mol dm⁻³, [AcOH] = 15% (v/v), temp. = 323 K.

^c[Cr^{VI}] = 1.66 × 10⁻³, [PhCHO] = 3.0 × 10⁻² and [HClO₄] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³, [AcOH] = 90% (v/v), temp. = 303 K.

^d[MnO₄⁻] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ and [PhCHO] = 6.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [AcOH] = 40% (v/v), temp. = 303 K.

^e[BrO₃⁻] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ and [PhCHO] = 5.0 × 10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³, [AcOH] = 70% (v/v), temp. = 323 K.

The positive H⁺ effect has been explained¹⁶ with the formation of effective oxidant species, V(OH)₃²⁺, which is formed between the reaction of V(OH)₄⁺ and H⁺. The reaction thus takes place between V(OH)₃²⁺ and the hydrated benzaldehyde^{25,26} to give an intermediate complex prior to electron transfer. However, the formation of the intermediate complex by the condensation of the reactive species seems unlikely which possibly occurs through the formation of transition state. The intermediate complex subsequently decomposes in a slow step to produce benzoic acid and other reaction products¹⁶.

Scheme 1

In this study¹⁶, vanadium(V) in its highest oxidation state (+5) has close similarities with chromium in its highest oxidation state (+6). The standard redox potential of the HCrO₄⁻-Cr³⁺ and V⁵⁺-V⁴⁺ couples are 1.195 and 1.00 V, respectively. Thus the present reaction mecha-

nism is quite similar with the established reaction mechanism during the oxidation of aromatic aldehyde by chromic acid¹⁹. Higher enthalpy of activation was found in the vanadium(V) assisted oxidation reactions where vanadium(V) behaves as a one electron transfer oxidant²⁷. However, the lower enthalpy of activation found in this study indicated the two electron transfer from vanadium(V) to the substrate and corroborated the above mechanism¹⁶.

Oxidation by chromium(VI) :

The oxidation of aromatic aldehydes by chromic acid has been studied¹⁹ in acid medium. The oxidation of these aldehydes occurs through the intermediate formation of an ester between the reactants. The rate at which chromium(VI) disappeared follows first order rate law and is not dependent on initial chromium(VI) concentration, where HCrO₄⁻ is the reacting species²⁸. The second order dependence of [H⁺] on reaction rate has been explained assuming that protonated chromic acid (H₃CrO₄⁺) reacts with hydrated benzaldehyde to give an intermediate ester which then decomposes to give the reaction products¹⁹. The rate of reaction decreases with electron-donating substituents but increases in the presence of electron-withdrawing substituents (Table 2). The reaction between hydrated benzaldehyde and protonated acid chromate ion occurs¹⁹ as shown below.

Scheme 2

The values of disproportionation constant for the rate-determining step are 2.8×10^{-4} , 5×10^{-4} , 10×10^{-4} and 20×10^{-4} (s^{-1}) at 313, 323, 333 and 343 K, respectively and the equilibrium constants¹⁹ for the formation of intermediate ester at the respective temperatures are 14.0, 10.0, 6.7 and 4.4 mol^{-1} . The value of equilibrium constant (K) was also determined²⁹ spectrophotometrically at 380 nm from the eq. (1). The differences in extinction ($\Delta\epsilon$) were measured from the two solutions both containing acid chromate and perchloric acid, one of the two solutions being added by benzaldehyde.

$$\Delta\epsilon/C = K \Delta\epsilon' l C_0 - K \Delta\epsilon \quad (1)$$

where, C = concentration of benzaldehyde, C_0 = concentration of acid chromate ion, l = optical path length in cm and $\Delta\epsilon'$ = the difference between the extinction coefficient of the complex and that of the acid chromate ion. The value of equilibrium constant has been calculated¹⁹ to be 20 mol^{-1} at 304.5 K from the plot of $\Delta\epsilon/C$ versus $\Delta\epsilon$.

An alternative reaction mechanism was also proposed¹⁹, where free benzaldehyde on protonation reacts with HCrO_4^- to give an intermediate ester which on further protonation gives protonated ester in fast equilibrium step. The protonated ester subsequently decomposes to give benzoic acid and Cr^{IV} through an internal two-electron transfer oxidation-reduction reaction. In perchloric acid medium, acid chromate ion (HCrO_4^-) is the dominating species which attacks the protonated aldehydes, however, in perchloric-acetic acid medium the attacking oxidant species is acetyl chromate ion ($\text{AcO}^+\text{CrO}_2^-$) (Scheme 3). Thus the oxidation of benzaldehyde with acetyl chromate is different from the chromic acid oxidation³⁰ so long as the attacking oxidant species is concerned.

Reduction potential data of several species of chro-

Scheme 3

mium provide information about the reactivity of its different species³¹. There is no evidence that free radicals are generated during the oxidation of aromatic aldehydes since acrylamide failed to polymerise¹⁹. The standard reduction potential of chromium(VI)-chromium(III) couple is 1.36 V as compared to chromium(V)-chromium(III) couple which is 1.75 V. Thus chromium(V) would behave as a highly reactive species and its reaction with the substrate would be very fast. In this study¹⁹, chromium(VI) reacts initially with the substrate to give benzoic acid and chromium(IV) which subsequently by reacting with chromium(VI) turns into chromium(V). Chromium(V) further reacts with benzaldehyde to give benzoic acid. Consequently one third of the total oxidation is affected by chromium(VI) and two third is affected by chromium(V). The steps of the reaction leading to the formation of chromium(III) may be represented as follows.

The existence of chromium(V) as an intermediate can be evidenced from the appearance of an absorption envelope at 465 nm during the spectrophotometric study of the oxidation of benzaldehyde³⁰ by chromyl acetate.

Oxidation by manganese(VII) :

The oxidation of aromatic aldehydes has been investigated in neutral medium and in phosphate buffer and acetic acid-water mixtures^{25,32}. The reactions have been studied earlier in carbonate buffer and aqueous KOH³³ but not in comparatively stronger acid media. The oxidation

kinetics of aromatic aldehydes by permanganate in comparatively stronger acid media has been studied¹⁷.

The kinetics of oxidation of PhCHO by permanganate ion¹⁷ in HClO₄ medium is first order with respect to [MnO₄⁻] whereas the order is less than one with respect to [aldehyde] as well as [H⁺]. The effect of substituents on the reaction rate has been studied in 40% (v/v) aqueous AcOH. Since the association constant (2.99 × 10⁻³) of the reaction H⁺ + MnO₄⁻ ⇌ HMnO₄ is quite low, protonation of MnO₄⁻ in the low acid concentration (0.03 to 0.3 M HClO₄) has been ruled out. The aldehyde molecule reacts¹⁷ with MnO₄⁻ and H⁺ to form an intermediate permanganate ester which subsequently decomposes in a slow step to give the reaction products. Mn^V which is generated in the slow step disproportionates to give Mn^{IV} and Mn^{VII}.

Scheme 4

The formation of Mn^V as an intermediate has been reported earlier^{25,32,33}. The plot of log *k*_{obs} versus Hammett substituent constant (σ) for the *meta*- and *para*-substituted methoxy-, Cl⁻ and nitro-benzaldehyde was found to bear a linear relationship with Hammett ρ value¹⁷ of -0.37. Wiberg and Stewart²⁵ studied the influence of substituents on the oxidation of benzaldehyde by MnO₄⁻ in presence of phosphate buffer which yielded the ρ value of -0.248 from Hammett plot. Although similar type of reaction mechanism was suggested in the above two studies, the different ρ values are attributed to different experimental conditions. The negative ρ value indicates that an electron donating group facilitated the reaction. Hence, in the present study, CH₃O- substituted benzaldehydes react at a faster rate than NO₂- and Cl- substituted benzaldehydes (Table 2). The equilibrium step forming the intermediate ester has a -ve ρ value which is larger than that for the rate determining step. Similar result has been recorded by Wiberg and Stewart²⁵ in the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes. Thus an electron withdrawing

group hinders the protonation of the aldehyde molecule in the equilibrium step thereby opposing the intermediate ester formation. However, an electron releasing group facilitates the protonation of the aldehyde and the protonated aldehyde is easily attacked by MnO₄⁻ ion to generate the intermediate ester in the equilibrium step¹⁷.

Oxidation by bromate :

The kinetics of oxidation of benzaldehyde and substituted derivatives by potassium bromate has been investigated in acetic acid medium¹⁸. The reaction is first order with respect to bromate and complex order with respect to the aldehyde. The effect of hydrogen ion concentration on the reaction at a fixed 70% (v/v) acetic acid concentration has been studied where the acidity was varied with the external addition of perchloric acid. The reaction rate was found to increase by 60% whenever perchloric acid concentration increased from 0.001 to 0.01 mol dm⁻³. Higher concentration of HClO₄ beyond 0.01 mol dm⁻³ was avoided in order to minimize bromination of benzaldehyde as experienced in sulphuric acid medium. The influence of dielectric constant on the rate was also studied. The rate increases with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium¹⁸ which suggests that the reaction taking place between ions of opposite charge. The reaction rate decreases in presence of electron-donating groups while it increases for electron-withdrawing groups attached with benzaldehyde molecule (Table 2).

From stoichiometry and product analysis it has been shown¹⁸ that 1 molar equivalent of potassium bromate oxidized approximately 3 molar equivalents of benzaldehyde under the experimental conditions. Two different mechanistic possibilities have been suggested¹⁸. In Scheme 5, the reaction has been shown to occur through the intermediate formation of bromate ester between hydrated benzaldehyde³⁴ and HBrO₃. The involvement of similar hydrated benzaldehyde has been proposed³⁵ in the oxidation of benzaldehydes by some other oxidants. The intermediate ester then transformed¹⁸ into benzoic acid and HBrO₂ in a slow step. HBrO₂ is subsequently reduced by another molecule of hydrated benzaldehyde to give benzoic acid and HBrO followed by its reduction with another molecule of the substrate to give product of reaction and HBr.

Scheme 5

An alternative mechanism was also suggested¹⁸ where the protonated aldehyde reacted with the BrO_3^- to give intermediate bromate ester prior to electron transfer (Scheme 6).

Scheme 6

The result concludes that benzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehydes are oxidized to give benzoic acid and respective substituted benzoic acids without bromination in acetic acid medium. Since the species H_2BrO_3^+ is very much susceptible towards reduction and the reactions are essentially diffusion controlled outer sphere process, formation of H_2BrO_3^+ and its participation in the reaction have been ruled out^{36,37}.

Oxidation by iridium(IV) :

The reactivity of benzaldehyde and some substituted benzaldehydes towards hexachloroiridate(IV) in acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer medium have been studied spectrophotometrically²⁰ in the pH range 3.23–4.63. The reaction is first order each in $[\text{Ir}^{\text{IV}}]$ and in [benzaldehyde]. The rate of reaction remains unchanged in the $\text{pH} < 3.0$, whereas it increases in the range of 3.23 to 4.63. The reaction was not carried out above pH 4.63 since iridium(IV) is reduced above this pH. The pseudo-first order rate constant was increased by three fold with the increase in pH from 3.23 to 4.6. The rate constant also

increases with an increase in sodium perchlorate, sodium chloride and sodium sulphate concentrations. The rate of oxidation of benzaldehyde increases with the decrease in acetic acid content (v/v) in the reaction medium. The reaction rate is significantly larger in lower acetic acid concentrations which indicate that hydrated benzaldehyde participates in the reaction as an effective reductant species²⁰.

The pseudo-first order rate constants for the oxidation of benzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehydes were determined in 5% (v/v) acetic acid medium. It has been observed that in case of *o*-methoxy benzaldehyde the rate constant increases to the extent of 70% whereas k_{obs} decreases to 68% in *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde²⁰. Similar result was also noticed in *meta*- and *para*-substituted methoxy- and nitro-benzaldehydes. The influence of vinyl compounds such as acrylamide and acrylonitrile on the rate of reaction was studied at different [acrylamide/acrylonitrile], but at constant [PhCHO], $[\text{Ir}^{\text{IV}}]$, pH and temperature. The decrease of the reaction rate with an increase in [acrylamide/acrylonitrile] was observed. When excess of methanol was added to the reaction mixture containing acrylamide white suspension was obtained indicating that free radicals were formed in solution during reaction²⁰.

The evidence of the formation of iridium-substrate complex was not established from the kinetic results²⁰. Hexachloroiridate(IV) seems to be stable³⁸ over a wide range of acidities. Under the experimental conditions ($[\text{Ir}^{\text{IV}}] = \sim 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 3.23\text{--}4.63$) IrCl_6^{2-} but not $\text{IrCl}_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$ oxidizes benzaldehyde to give benzoic acid and iridium(III) although photochemical aquation³⁹ of IrCl_6^{2-} in the UV region leading to the formation of $\text{IrCl}_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$ takes place at high acidity and high $[\text{Ir}^{\text{IV}}]$ ²⁰. The effect of addition of Ir^{III} was studied in the ratio of $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]/[\text{Ir}^{\text{IV}}] = 10$. The pseudo-first order rate constant was found to be independent of $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$, which excluded the back reaction²⁰ between the free radical and Ir^{III} . Iridium(IV) is an one electron transfer oxidant, hence, the transfer of hydride ion from the hydrated aldehyde has been ruled out. IrCl_6^{2-} initially attacks²⁰ the C-H bond of the hydrated benzaldehyde to produce free radical and IrCl_6^{3-} . Free radical further reacts with another molecule of IrCl_6^{2-} to give benzoic acid and IrCl_6^{3-} by outer sphere

process.

Scheme 7

The isolation of the reaction products indicated that PhCOCOPh was not produced in this oxidation reaction. This speaks for the fast reaction of the free radical with iridium(IV) to produce benzoic acid²⁰. Mass spectrometry of the reaction products confirmed the absence of chlorinated products^{40,41} (which might have been produced due to the active participation of ligand environment in IrCl_6^{2-}) which unequivocally suggests that the reaction occurs through an outer sphere mechanism.

Oxidation by $[\text{M}^{\text{III}}(\text{H}_2\text{TeO}_6)_2]^{5-}$ ($\text{M}^{\text{III}} = \text{Cu}^{\text{III}}$ and Ag^{III}):

The reactivity of few aromatic aldehydes towards dihydrogentelluratometallate(III) ($[\text{M}^{\text{III}}(\text{H}_2\text{TeO}_6)_2]^{5-}$, where $\text{M}^{\text{III}} = \text{Cu}^{\text{III}}$ or Ag^{III}) have been reported²¹ in alkaline medium ($[\text{OH}^-] = 0.016\text{--}0.16 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$). Details of preparations and spectral measurements of $[\text{M}^{\text{III}}(\text{H}_2\text{TeO}_6)_2]^{5-}$ are mentioned elsewhere^{42–45}. The aldehydes are oxidized according to the following eqs. (5) and (6).

where, X = -H, -NO₂, -Cl and -OCH₃.

After the kinetic experiments, a portion of the filtrate of each respective reaction mixture containing the oxidized aldehyde product was treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid to obtain the white crystals of organic acids²¹. The acids were extracted with chloroform. On removal of the solvent, a colorless solid organic acid was separated. The organic acids were identified by comparing their m.ps. with the known samples. Again, another portion of the reaction mixture was left for an hour when green and black precipitate²¹ was obtained from Cu^{III} and Ag^{III} containing solution respectively. The green product was found to be paramagnetic. The EPR spectra of the solution corresponding to the oxidation of benzalde-

hyde by ditelluratocuprate(III) complex indicated²¹ that the peak intensity had increased with the progress of the reaction due to the formation of paramagnetic d^9 copper(II) species. The formation of copper(II) species was further supported by the fact that solid green precipitate when dissolved in dilute perchloric acid and then made ammoniacal, formed a deep blue colored solution due to the formation of cupraammine complex²¹. Similar observations have also been noticed upon oxidation^{46–49} of H_2PO_2^- , HPO_3^{2-} , NO_2^- and N_3^- by copper(III) complex. For the other reaction, the black precipitate when dissolved in dilute nitric acid and the solution so obtained was treated with potassium iodide gave a yellow precipitate of silver iodide. This confirmed the formation of Ag^{I} species²¹.

The reactions are first order each in $[\text{XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CHO}]$ and $[\text{M}^{\text{III}}(\text{H}_2\text{TeO}_6)_2]^{5-}$ but independent of $[\text{OH}^-]$ ²¹. Between the dihydrogentelluratometallate(III) complexes, $[\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}(\text{H}_2\text{TeO}_6)_2]^{5-}$ reacts with aromatic aldehydes at much faster rates than $[\text{Ag}^{\text{III}}(\text{H}_2\text{TeO}_6)_2]^{5-}$. Since the oxidation of benzaldehydes have been carried out at much lower $[\text{OH}^-]$ ($< 0.016 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), the formation of ionized gem diols $[\text{PhCH(OH)O}]^{50,51}$ and its participation in the reactions with copper(III) and silver(III) complexes have been ignored. Again, since the rate is independent of $[\text{OH}^-]$, $\text{XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CHO}$ reacts with $[\text{M}^{\text{III}}(\text{H}_2\text{TeO}_6)_2]^{5-}$ to give the reaction products²¹. The influence of substituents at the *m*- and *p*-positions of benzaldehyde has been studied.

The reaction takes place through the intermediate formation of $\text{XC}_6\text{H}_4\dot{\text{C}}=\text{O}$ and $\text{XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{C}^+=\text{O}$ followed by its reaction with OH^- to give respective substituted carboxylate ions²¹.

Scheme 8

Of these two oxidants silver(III) reduction can involve

place according to the scheme outlined below.

Scheme 10

Hexacyanoferrate(III) oxidation of benzaldehyde proceeds at slower rate than aliphatic aldehydes (other than formaldehyde). The plots of entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) versus enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) for the enolizable and non-enolizable aldehydes gave two different straight lines which indicated that two different mechanisms had been operative in these reactions²².

For $\text{K}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ which is an inert metal complex, rapid electron transfer occurs rather than ligand substitution in the redox reactions. It has been reported that the absorption spectrum of hexacyanoferrate(III) in the region 300–500 nm remains same in the alkaline medium (0.005–1.0) mol dm⁻³. Hence in alkaline medium CN⁻ ligand of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ is not replaced by OH⁻ and the oxidation takes place by the stable $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ through non bonded electron transfer process²².

Discussion

The oxidation reactions involving different metal ion oxidants were carried out in aqueous medium. Since the atmospheric oxidation of benzaldehyde may occur during kinetic studies the behavior of aromatic aldehydes in absence of the oxidants prior to kinetic experiments has been studied. A solution of benzaldehyde in sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer was worked up for benzoic acid. The amount of benzoic acid was less than 0.5% in a freshly prepared solution and remains almost unaltered even on standing for three months at room temperature in a stoppered bottle. Thus the possibility of aerial oxidation to benzoic acid under kinetic condition has been ruled out. The yields of benzoic acid were noted for different

reactions. The yields to the extent of 80% and 95% benzoic acid were obtained in the oxidations of benzaldehyde by vanadium(V)¹⁶ and chromium(VI)¹⁹ respectively. It has been reported¹⁸ that 1 molar equivalent of potassium bromate oxidized 3 molar equivalent of benzaldehyde taking into consideration that potassium bromide is formed in the reaction. A stoichiometry of 2 mol IrCl_6^{2-} per mole of benzaldehyde indicates that benzaldehyde is quantitatively oxidized to benzoic acid²⁰. In oxidation of the aromatic aldehydes by $[\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}(\text{H}_2\text{TeO}_6)_2]^{5-}$ ²¹, $[\text{Ag}^{\text{III}}(\text{H}_2\text{TeO}_6)_2]^{5-}$ ²¹ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ ²² in alkaline medium the products have been obtained as sodium salts of the respective acids which upon acidification gave benzoic acid and substituted benzoic acids. The yields have been calculated to be 68, 59 and 71% in the oxidation of benzaldehyde by copper(III), silver(III) complexes and $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ respectively.

The kinetic results for the oxidation of benzaldehyde by different oxidants in acid medium are presented in Table 1. The rate constants for the oxidation of benzaldehyde and substituted compounds by V^{V} ¹⁶, Cr^{VI} ¹⁹, MnO_4^- ¹⁷ and BrO_3^- ¹⁸ in acid medium are recorded in Table 2. In the oxidations by chromium(VI)¹⁹ and bromate¹⁸ the rates are strongly accelerated by electron withdrawing groups whereas those are retarded in presence of electron donating groups (Table 2). The second order rate constants for the oxidation of benzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehydes by Cu^{III} ²¹, Ag^{III} ²¹ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ ²² complexes follow the order : $-\text{NO}_2 > -\text{H} > -\text{Cl} > -\text{OCH}_3$ (Table 3). The values of k_0 and k for each reaction in absence and presence of substituents respectively are related by the expression⁵⁴; $\log k/k_0 = \rho\sigma$, where ρ = constant and σ = Hammett substitution constant whose value remains constant for a specific substituent in a specific position (*m*- or *p*-). The values of σ for *meta*- or *para*-substituents are taken from the literature⁵⁵. A glance at the Table 4 shows that ρ values with chromium(VI) and bromate are 1.02 and 1.05 respectively in the acid medium. The values of ρ which are negative have been calculated to be -0.704 and -0.37 for the oxidations by vanadium(V) and manganese(VII) respectively. No attempt has been made to calculate ρ for the oxidations by iridium(IV) since substitution effects were studied using *ortho*-substituted derivatives and reliable σ values for *ortho*-substituted benzaldehydes are not available in the

Table 3. The values of second-order rate constants for the oxidation of benzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehyde by Cu^{III}, Ag^{III} and Fe(CN)₆³⁻ complex in 15 % *t*-butyl alcohol

Substrate	10 ² k ₂ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)		
	^f [Cu ^{III} (H ₂ TeO ₆) ₂] ⁵⁻ (Ref. 21)	^g [Ag ^{III} (H ₂ TeO ₆) ₂] ⁵⁻ (Ref. 21)	^g [Fe(CN) ₆] ³⁻ (Ref. 22)
Benzaldehyde	2.25 ± 0.14	0.94 ± 0.04	12.33 ± 0.51
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	6.67 ± 0.31	1.37 ± 0.07	64.4 ± 1.8
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	4.17 ± 0.17	0.99 ± 0.02	18.8 ± 0.66
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	4.98 ± 0.27	1.08 ± 0.04	52.9 ± 1.93
<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	2.08 ± 0.08	0.35 ± 0.01	11.0 ± 0.44
<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	1.92 ± 0.09	0.25 ± 0.02	11.8 ± 0.49
<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	0.93 ± 0.04	0.13 ± 0.004	9.41 ± 0.46
<i>o</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde	1.28 ± 0.05	0.25 ± 0.01	6.07 ± 0.19
<i>m</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde	0.95 ± 0.05	0.19 ± 0.007	8.33 ± 0.35
<i>p</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde	0.072 ± 0.03	0.12 ± 0.006	4.72 ± 0.13

The errors correspond to two least-squares standard deviations (±2σ). ^fAt 298 K. ^gAt 313 K.

Table 4. The values of different reactions parameters for the oxidation reactions in acid as well as in alkaline medium

Oxidant	Medium	Cell reaction	E ₀ (V)	k _H /k _D	ρ	ΔH [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS [‡] (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
Vanadium(V)	HClO ₄	V(OH) ₄ ⁺ + 2H ⁺ + e ⇌ VO ₂ ⁺ + 3H ₂ O (Ref. 59)	1.00	4.3	-0.704	23.0	-252.8
		V ^V ⇌ V ^{III} (Ref. 24)	0.68				
Chromium (VI)	HClO ₄	Cr ₂ O ₇ ²⁻ + 14H ⁺ + 6e ⇌ 2Cr ³⁺ + 7H ₂ O (Ref. 60)	1.36	3.5	1.05	55.8	-135.3
Manganese(VII)	40% AcOH	MnO ₄ ⁻ + 8H ⁺ + 5e ⇌ Mn ²⁺ + 4H ₂ O (Ref. 59)	1.51	5.0	-0.37	37.5	-126
	(v/v) and HClO ₄	MnO ₄ ⁻ + 4H ⁺ + 3e ⇌ MnO ₂ + 2H ₂ O	1.695				
Bromate	AcOH and HClO ₄	BrO ₃ ⁻ + 6H ⁺ + 6e ⇌ Br ⁻ + 3H ₂ O (Ref. 61)	1.423	4.8	1.02	57.8	-133.2
Iridium(IV)	AcOH-NaOAc	IrCl ₆ ²⁻ + e ⇌ IrCl ₆ ³⁻ (Ref. 59)	1.02	7.0	*	112.0	81.2
Cu ^{III}	KOH	[Cu ^{III} (H ₂ TeO ₆) ₂] ⁵⁻ + e ⇌ [Cu ^{II} (H ₂ TeO ₆) ₂] ⁶⁻ (Ref. 49)	-0.506	4.5	0.85	37.5	-153
Ag ^{III}	KOH	[Ag ^{III} (H ₂ TeO ₆) ₂] ⁵⁻ + 2e ⇌ [Ag ^I (H ₂ TeO ₆) ₂] ⁷⁻ (Ref. 49)	-0.571	4.14	0.84	82	-24
[Fe(CN) ₆] ³⁻	KOH	[Fe(CN) ₆] ³⁻ + e ⇌ [Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻ (Ref. 61)	0.36	1.93	0.6488	51	-132

*Since the substituent effects have been studied with *ortho*-substituted derivatives and the values of σ are not mentioned in the literature, no attempt has been made to calculate ρ.

literature. On the other hand, ρ values are positive and found in the region (0.65–0.84) in the oxidations of aromatic aldehydes by [Cu(H₂TeO₆)₂]⁵⁻, [Ag(H₂TeO₆)₂]⁵⁻ and [Fe(CN)₆]³⁻. There is also literature evidence³³ that oxidation of aromatic aldehydes by alkaline permanganate is strongly accelerated by electron withdrawing groups and revealed by the Hammett ρ value^{25,33,56} of +1.83 at

pH 12.6. Aspects of the oxidation of mono substituted benzaldehydes to corresponding benzoic acids by bromine have been reported by McTigue and Sime³⁴ and then by Barker and Dahm³⁵. When log k₂ were plotted against σ, two parallel lines were obtained, one for *m*-substituted derivatives and the other for *p*-substituted derivatives. All rate differences in each of *m*- or *p*-substi-

tuted derivatives are small unlike present studies and the line drawn to correlate benzaldehyde and its *m*-derivatives with σ has a slope corresponding to +0.17. However, it has been shown that *p*-nitro benzaldehyde is oxidized three times faster than benzaldehyde by bromine.

The reactions have been studied in the oxidation of benzaldehyde and substituted derivatives under comparable condition of experiments. The rate of oxidation increases in case of methoxy benzaldehyde while decreases for nitro benzaldehyde by both vanadium(V) and iridium(IV) in acid medium (Table 2). Both these reactions occur between ions of charged and uncharged molecules. The experimental evidence supports the formation of acyclic complex between $V(OH)_4^+$ and PhCHO whereas electron transfer from substrate to $IrCl_6^{2-}$ takes place leading to the formation of free radical and $IrCl_6^{3-}$ without any evidence for intermediate complex formation. Again when the oxidation of benzaldehyde by chromium(VI)¹⁹ was performed in perchloric acid medium, acid chromate ion ($HCrO_4^-$) reacts with the protonated aldehyde but in mixed acid medium (perchloric acid-acetic acid) the reacting oxidant species is acetyl chromate ion ($AcO-CrO_2O^-$). AcO^- is a better leaving group compared to HO^- , which indicates that the elimination of HOAc from the protonated ester is faster than that of H_2O . Thus the rate of oxidation is higher in perchloric-acetic acid medium than in perchloric acid medium only. The rate of oxidation of benzaldehyde increases for an electron withdrawing substituent and decreases for an electron donating group (Table 2). This is due to the fact¹⁹ that the benzylic C^+ of *p*-nitro benzaldehyde is never neutralized by electromeric shift and it is available for reacting with $HCrO_4^-$ to form chromate ester. However, in case of *p*-methoxy benzaldehyde the benzylic carbocation (C^+) is neutralized through resonance and thereby diminishes the nucleophilic attack by $HCrO_4^-$ to get the intermediate ester. It may be mentioned that the generation of RC^+HOH during the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes is less favorable owing to the presence of alkyl group attached with -CHO group. Thus, the formation of intermediate ester in the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes^{19b} by chromium(VI) was found to be insignificant. This also supported the above mechanism in the oxidation of aromatic aldehydes by chromium(VI).

The oxidation of benzaldehyde by bromate¹⁸ occurs

through the formation of intermediate bromate ester. The formation of intermediate bromate ester will depend on the electron withdrawing and electron attracting substituents attached to aromatic ring. The structural feature which tends to diminish the accumulation of positive charge on the benzylic carbon decreases the rate of reaction. Consequently an electron releasing group (e.g. $-OCH_3$ group) attached to the aromatic ring in benzaldehyde makes the oxidation rate slower unlike an electron attracting group (e.g. $-NO_2$ group). Chlorine substituted benzaldehyde decreased the rate slightly than that of unsubstituted benzaldehyde.

The aromatic aldehydes are oxidized by one- or two-electron transfer oxidants. The oxidation of benzoic acid in almost quantitative yield indicates that PhCOCOPh is not formed during the oxidation of PhCHO by iridium(IV)²⁰. On the other hand, such a possibility that PhCOCOPh is formed in the oxidation by two electron transfer oxidants like chromium(VI)¹⁹ and BrO_3^- ¹⁸ has been ruled out since two electrons are transferred from substrates to oxidants in the rate determining step to give benzoic acid and substituted benzoic acids and yields to the extent of 70% or above have been obtained. The oxidation reactions occur by C-H bond cleavage and are supported by the determination of rate constants in the oxidations of PhCHO and PhCDO followed by the calculation of k_H/k_D ratios under comparable conditions of each reaction (Table 4). The values of k_H/k_D in the region (3.5–7.0) have been obtained except in the oxidation of PhCHO by $Fe(CN)_6^{3-}$ ²² in alkaline medium where k_H/k_D is 1.93. The lower value in $[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-}$ may be due to the fact that E_0 value is much lower (0.36 V) in alkaline medium as compared to the other oxidants. However, the lower values of k_H/k_D in the region (0.35–1.15) and (0.7–2.38) have also been obtained in several acid catalyzed and base catalyzed reactions⁵⁴ respectively as well as in the oxidations of several organic reductants by different metal ion oxidants^{57,58} like manganese(III), vanadium(V) and cobalt(III) in the regions (1.1–1.6), (0.42–2.0) and (0.9–2.3) respectively. The oxidation of aromatic aldehydes by bromine (E_0 for $Br_2 + 2e \rightleftharpoons 2Br^-$ is 1.087 V at 298 K) has been studied by Barker and Dahm³⁵ in buffers of pH 1–5 in aqueous acetic acid. The substituents of ten substituted benzaldehydes have little effect on the rate of oxidation. The value of k_H/k_D have been found

to be 2.5. The oxidation has been shown to occur where hydride ion is removed from the hydrated aldehyde by bromine.

Scheme 11

The experiments have been carried out at 343 K contrary to the experiments with transition metal ion oxidants which have been studied at lower temperatures. Consequently such a possibility that hydride ion is removed has been ignored with transition metal ion oxidants and BrO_3^- .

The oxidations by IrCl_6^{2-} and $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ occur by outer-sphere electron transfer process whereas by other oxidants by inner sphere mechanism. Thus, irrespective of whether the reactions have been studied in acid or alkaline medium the products of oxidation are benzoic acid and substituted benzoic acids or their sodium salts. Again complex kinetic rate expressions have been obtained in acid medium unlike those in alkaline medium which are kinetically simple. The plot of $\log K$ versus $1/T$ (where K is the equilibrium constant for the reactions which occur by intermediate complex formation) gave straight lines from which the values of thermodynamic parameters ΔH° and ΔS° were calculated. The plot of ΔS° versus ΔH° is linear (Fig. 1) for the oxidation of

Fig. 1. Plots of ΔS° versus ΔH° for the oxidation of benzaldehyde by different oxidant in acid medium : (a) vanadium(V); (b) chromium(VI); (c) MnO_4^- ; (d) BrO_3^- .

benzaldehydes by V^{V} ¹⁶, Cr^{VI} ¹⁹, MnO_4^- ¹⁷ and BrO_3^- ¹⁸ in acid medium. Again entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) is linearly related to the enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) for the oxidation of benzaldehyde by different oxidants, although two different lines were obtained (Figs. 2 and 3) for the reactions occurring in acid and alkaline medium. An attempt was also made to correlate activation parameters with redox potentials of different couples. The plots of E_0 against ΔS^\ddagger or ΔH^\ddagger failed to follow a linear relationship rather scattered diagram is obtained. On the other hand

Fig. 2. Isokinetic correlation for the oxidation of benzaldehyde by different oxidant in acid medium. Plot of ΔS^\ddagger versus ΔH^\ddagger : (a) vanadium(V); (b) chromium(VI); (c) MnO_4^- ; (d) BrO_3^- ; (e) iridium(IV).

Fig. 3. Isokinetic correlation for the oxidation of benzaldehyde by different oxidant in alkaline medium. Plot of ΔS^\ddagger versus ΔH^\ddagger : (a) Cu^{III} ; (b) Ag^{III} ; (c) $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$.

disproportionation constants (k) of different reactions increase with the increase in E_0 in acid medium and when plotted against E_0 a curve is obtained. No attempt has been made to correlate second order rate constants with E_0 for the oxidation of the substrates in alkaline medium since reliable data on redox potentials of copper(III) and silver(III) complexes²¹ are not available and the values reported in Table 4 are based on cyclic voltammetric measurements.

Conclusion

The reactions are highly dependent on reaction conditions and are characterized by different mechanistic behaviours. These are supported by different values of k_H/k_D , ρ , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger as shown in Table 4. This review thus highlights the kinetics and mechanism of electron transfer reactions for the oxidation of a host of aromatic aldehydes employing the various transition metal ions as well as bromate as different oxidants. It is hoped that the article will stimulate further research on the oxidation by some other transition metal ion oxidants and then it would be much more important than what it is today.

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